

Double-Double Laminates: Homogenisation, Mechanical Performance and Compression After Impact

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Double-Double

Prof. Stephen Tsai
and Aidan Hawkins
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Introduction

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Traditional Quad Laminates

Collection of
 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$ & 90°
plies

Same
principle since
the 1960s

- Large number of stacking sequence permutations
(>1 Million for a 32 ply laminate)
- Layup constrained by 30+ legacy rules [3]

.....

→ Stacking sequence optimisation is virtually impossible

- Internal discontinuities
- Resin pockets
- Ply wrinkles
- More difficult to detect defects

[3] J. A. Bailie, R. P. Ley, and A. Pasricha. A Summary of Composite Laminate Guidelines. 1997.

[4] Irisarri, F.-X. *et al.* (2014) 'Optimal design of laminated composite structures with ply drops using stacking sequence tables'

Double-Double Laminates

Proposed by
Prof. Stephen
Tsai in 2017 [5].

Removes the design
limitations imposed
by quad laminates

Simplify the design
and manufacturing of
composite laminates

Bi-Angle Set 1

+

Bi-Angle Set 2

=

Double – Double

Double-Double Laminates

Homogenisation of Double- Double Laminates

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Homogenisation of DD Laminates

How many sub-laminate repeats are needed to meet the homogenisation criteria [8]?

$$|D^{Tr*} - A^{Tr*}| < 0.02 \quad \& \quad B^{Tr*} < 0.02$$

Thickness normalised terms based on Master Ply values

What sequence of angles within the sub-laminate minimises the required repeats?

$$[\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi], [+ \Phi / - \Psi / - \Phi / + \Psi], [+ \Phi / - \Psi / + \Psi / - \Phi] \dots$$

Homogenisation of DD Laminates

Aim is to prevent laminate warpage

Sub-laminate repeats to satisfy original homogenisation criteria [8]

$$|D^{Tr*} - A^{Tr*}| < 0.02 \quad \& \quad B^{Tr*} < 0.02$$

Sequence of angles minimising the required repeats?

$$[\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi], [+ \Phi/-\Psi/-\Phi/+ \Psi], [+ \Phi/-\Psi /+ \Psi /-\Phi] \dots$$

Homogenisation of DD Laminates

DD Homogenisation Grid

Sub-laminate repeats to satisfy original homogenisation criteria [8]

$$|D^{Tr*} - A^{Tr*}| < 0.02 \quad \& \quad B^{Tr*} < 0.02$$

Sequence of angles minimising the required repeats?

$$[\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi], [+ \Phi/-\Psi/-\Phi/+ \Psi], [+ \Phi/-\Psi /+ \Psi /-\Phi].....$$

Experimental Homogenisation Results

Original homogenisation criteria [8]

$$|D^{Tr*} - A^{Tr*}| < 0.02 \quad \& \quad B^{Tr*} < 0.02$$

Manufactured Panels IM7 977-2 Prepreg

$[22.5/-67.5/-22.5/67.5]_4$

$[22.5/-67.5/67.5/-22.5]_4$

$[9, -47, -9, 47]_5$

[8] Vermes, B. et al. (2021) 'Application of the Tsai's modulus and double-double concepts to the definition of a new affordable design approach for composite laminates', *Composite Structures*, 259, p. 113246.

Experimental Homogenisation Results

Original homogenisation criteria [8]

$$|D^{Tr*} - A^{Tr*}| < 0.02 \quad \& \quad B^{Tr*} < 0.02$$

Panels exhibited warpage

Conclusion:

The "arbitrary" 2% homogenisation criteria [8] is not sufficient to prevent warpage

Point cloud data from surface scanning

[8] Vermes, B. *et al.* (2021) 'Application of the Tsai's modulus and double-double concepts to the definition of a new affordable design approach for composite laminates', *Composite Structures*, 259, p. 113246.

Updated Homogenisation Criteria

*Proposing updated homogenisation
criteria:*

$$|D^{Tr*} - A^{Tr*}| < 0.02 \quad \& \quad B^{Tr*} < 0.01$$

Updated Homogenisation Criteria

Proposing updated homogenisation criteria:

$$|D^{Tr*} - A^{Tr*}| < 0.02 \quad \& \quad B^{Tr*} < 0.01$$

Laminates manufactured meeting these criteria, have shown very minimal to negligible warpage

Updated Homogenisation Criteria

Proposing updated homogenisation criteria:

$$|D^{Tr*} - A^{Tr*}| < 0.02 \quad \& \quad B^{Tr*} < 0.01$$

Minimal to zero warpage

$[22.5/-67.5/-22.5/67.5]_8$

Updated Homogenisation Criteria

Proposing updated homogenisation criteria:

$$|D^{Tr*} - A^{Tr*}| < 0.02 \quad \& \quad B^{Tr*} < 0.01$$

For some angle combinations minimum of 8 sub-laminate repeats

One Step Further

Symmetry-Enhanced Double-Double (SEDD) Laminates

Symmetry-Enhanced Double-Double (SEDD) Laminates

SEDD-1
 $[(BB)_s / (BB)_r]_T$

Symmetric DD sub-laminate
as foundation

Advantage?

Homogenisation criteria
satisfied with a lower number
of sub-laminate repeats

SEDD-2
 $[(BB)_{s,r} / (BB)_n]_T$
Where $r \geq 1$ and $n = 0$ or 1

BB = Building Block (sub-laminate)

Symmetry-Enhanced Double-Double (SEDD) Laminates

Symmetric DD sub-laminate as foundation

Advantage?

Homogenisation criteria satisfied with a lower number of sub-laminate repeats

Updated homogenisation criteria:

$$|D^{Tr*} - A^{Tr*}| < 0.02 \quad \& \quad B^{Tr*} < 0.01$$

BB = Building Block (sub-laminate)

Symmetry-Enhanced Double-Double (SEDD) Laminates

Maximum B^{Tr*} Term for $[22.5/-67.5/-22.5/67.5]_r$

Original DD Stacking Sequence: $[BB]_{rT}$

For some angle combinations minimum 8 BB's

Symmetry-Enhanced Double-Double (SEDD) Laminates

$B^{Tr*} < 0.01$ criterion met with ≥ 2 BB's

for any angle combination

Symmetry-Enhanced Double-Double (SEDD) Laminates

Maintain the ability to taper with ply drops on the external faces

Can taper to a much thinner laminate

Mechanical Performance of Double-Double Laminates

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Lamination Parameters

Lamination parameters describe the stiffness properties of a laminate independent of the ply material

Lamination Parameters

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_{11}^* \\ A_{22}^* \\ A_{12}^* \\ A_{66}^* \\ A_{16}^* \\ A_{26}^* \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & V_1 & V_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -V_1 & V_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -V_2 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -V_2 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & V_3/2 & V_4 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & V_3/2 & -V_4 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \\ U_4 \\ U_5 \end{bmatrix}$$

Material Invariants

Thickness normalised in-plane matrix terms

Lamination Parameters

Lamination parameters describe the stiffness properties of a laminate independent of the ply material

Lamination Parameters

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_{11}^* \\ A_{22}^* \\ A_{12}^* \\ A_{66}^* \\ A_{16}^* \\ A_{26}^* \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & V_1 & V_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -V_1 & V_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -V_2 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -V_2 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & V_3/2 & V_4 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & V_3/2 & -V_4 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \\ U_4 \\ U_5 \end{bmatrix}$$

Material Invariants

Thickness normalised in-plane matrix terms

Double - Double

Lamination Parameter Plot
Standard DD ($\pm\phi, \pm\psi$)

Conversion to DD Sub-Laminates

A framework has been established to convert any CFRP laminate to DD sub-laminate

$$\cos(2\psi) = V_1 + \sqrt{-V_1^2 + \frac{V_2}{2} + \frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\cos(2\phi) = 2V_1 - \cos(2\psi)$$

$V_1, V_2 =$ Lamination Parameters

Conversion to DD Sub-Laminates

A framework has been established to convert any CFRP laminate to DD sub-laminate

$$\cos(2\psi) = V_1 + \sqrt{-V_1^2 + \frac{V_2}{2} + \frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\cos(2\phi) = 2V_1 - \cos(2\psi)$$

Test Laminates

Laminate	Quad Layup	In-Plane (DD-A) Match	Out-of-Plane (DD-D) Match
Soft	$[\pm 45/0/\pm 45/90/\pm 45]_s$	$[(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)_{s2}/(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)]_T$	$[(27.5/-55.5/-27.5/55.5)_{s2}/(27.5/-55.5/-27.5/55.5)]_T$
Quasi	$[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$	$[22.5/-67.5/67.5/-22.5]_4$	$[9/-61/61/-9]_4$
Hard1	$[45_2/0_4/-45_2/90_2]_s$	$[9/-61.5/61.5/-9]_5$	$[9/-47/47/-9]_5$
Hard2	$[45/0_2/-45/90_2/-45/0_2/45]_s$		$[(7.5/-58/58/-7.5)_{s2}/(7.5/-58/58/-7.5)]_1T$

Test Laminates

Laminate	Quad Layup	In-Plane (DD-A) Match	Out-of-Plane (DD-D) Match
Soft	$[\pm 45/0/\pm 45/90/\pm 45]_s$	$[(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)_{s2}/(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)]_T$	$[(27.5/-55.5/-27.5/55.5)_{s2}/(27.5/-55.5/-27.5/55.5)]_T$
Quasi	$[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$	$[22.5/-67.5/67.5/-22.5]_4$	$[9/-61/61/-9]_4$
Hard1	$[45_2/0_4/-45_2/90_2]_s$	$[9/-61.5/61.5/-9]_5$	$[9/-47/47/-9]_5$
Hard2	$[45/0_2/-45/90_2/-45/0_2/45]_s$		$[(7.5/-58/58/-7.5)_{s2}/(7.5/-58/58/-7.5)]_T$

In-Plane LPP

Out-Of-Plane LPP

Test Laminates

Laminate	Quad Layup	In-Plane (DD-A) Match	Out-of-Plane (DD-D) Match
Soft	$[\pm 45/0/\pm 45/90/\pm 45_2]_s$	$[(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)_{s2}/(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)]_T$	$[(27.5/-55.5/-27.5/55.5)_{s2}/(27.5/-55.5/-27.5/55.5)]_T$
Quasi	$[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$	$[22.5/-67.5/67.5/-22.5]_4$	$[9/-61/61/-9]_4$
Hard1	$[45_2/0_4/-45_2/90_2]_s$		$[9/-47/47/-9]_5$
Hard2	$[45/0_2/-45/90_2/-45/0_2/45]_s$	$[9/-61.5/61.5/-9]_5$	$[(7.5/-58/58/-7.5)_{s2}/(7.5/-58/58/-7.5)]_1_T$

Unnotched
Tension

Unnotched
Compression

Open-Hole
Tension

Open-Hole
Compression

Flexural
3-Point-Bend

Conversion Framework Validation: In-plane

A framework has been established to convert any CFRP laminate to DD sub-laminate

Laminate	Quad Layup	In-Plane (DD-A) Match
Soft	$[\pm 45/0/\pm 45/90/\pm 45]_s$	$[(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)_{s2}/(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)]_T$
Quasi	$[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$	$[22.5/-67.5/67.5/-22.5]_4$
Hard1	$[45_2/0_4/-45_2/90_2]_s$	$[9/-61.5/61.5/-9]_s$
Hard2	$[45/0_2/-45/90_2/-45/0_2/45]_s$	

Young's modulus comparison CLT vs Quad vs DD for a range of laminates

Unnotched Tensile Strength - First Ply Failure

Average increase of 7.49% for the DD in
FPF strength

First Ply Failure (FPF) comparison Quad vs DD for a range of laminates

Laminate	Quad Layup	In-Plane (DD-A) Match
Soft	$[\pm 45/0/\pm 45/90/\pm 45]_s$	$[(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)_{s2}/(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)]_T$
Quasi	$[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$	$[22.5/-67.5/67.5/-22.5]_4$
Hard1	$[45_2/0_4/-45_2/90_2]_s$	$[9/-61.5/61.5/-9]_5$
Hard2	$[45/0_2/-45/90_2/-45/0_2/45]_s$	

Unnotched Tensile Strength – Ultimate Strength

Average decrease of 5.64% in experimental ultimate strength for the DD laminate

Unnotched tensile experimental ultimate strength comparison
Quad vs DD for a range of laminates

Laminate	Quad Layup	In-Plane (DD-A) Match
Soft	$[\pm 45/0/\pm 45/90/\pm 45]_s$	$[(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)_{s2}/(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)]_T$
Quasi	$[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$	$[22.5/-67.5/67.5/-22.5]_4$
Hard1	$[45_2/0_4/-45_2/90_2]_s$	$[9/-61.5/61.5/-9]_5$
Hard2	$[45/0_2/-45/90_2/-45/0_2/45]_s$	

Why are these laminates of equivalent stiffness failing at different stresses?

Unnotched Tensile Strength – Ultimate Strength

Why are these laminates of equivalent stiffness failing at different stresses?

Conduct progressive failure analysis:

- Determine ply failure modes
- Predict Last Ply Failure (LPF) strengths

Unnotched tensile LPF and experimental ultimate strength comparison Quad vs DD for a range of laminates

Quasi Quad

Ply No.	Angle (°)	Final Failure
1	0	FT
2	45	MT
3	90	FC
4	-45	FT
5	0	FT
6	45	MT
7	90	FC
8	-45	FT
9	-45	FT
10	90	FC
11	45	MT
12	0	FT
13	-45	FT
14	90	FC
15	45	MT
16	0	FT

Laminate failure dominated by fibre failure

Quasi DD-A

Ply No.	Angle (°)	Final Failure
1	22.5	FT
2	-67.5	MT
3	67.5	MT
4	-22.5	FT
5	22.5	FT
6	-67.5	MT
7	67.5	MT
8	-22.5	FT
9	22.2	FT
10	-67.5	MT
11	67.5	MT
12	-22.5	FT
13	22.5	FT
14	-67.5	MT
15	67.5	MT
16	-22.5	FT

Laminate failure dominated by matrix failure

Unnotched Tensile Strength – Ultimate Strength

Why are these laminates of equivalent stiffness failing at different stresses?

Conduct progressive failure analysis:

- Determine ply failure modes
- Predict Last Ply Failure (LPF) strengths

Unnotched tensile LPF and experimental ultimate strength comparison Quad vs DD for a range of laminates

Interlaminar stress comparison of Quad and DD laminates.

Unnotched Compressive Strength

Laminate	Quad Layup	In-Plane (DD-A) Match
Soft	$[\pm 45/0/\pm 45/90/\pm 45]_s$	$[(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)_{s2}/(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)]_T$
Quasi	$[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$	$[22.5/-67.5/67.5/-22.5]_4$
Hard1	$[45_2/0_4/-45_2/90_2]_s$	$[9/-61.5/61.5/-9]_5$
Hard2	$[45/0_2/-45/90_2/-45/0_2/45]_s$	

- Average 9.22% increase in unnotched compressive strength for the DD laminate.
- Analysis of the compressive failure modes from the specimens is being used to explain the failure trends observed

Hard1 Quad E1

Hard1 DD-A E1

Unnotched compression experimental ultimate strength comparison Quad vs DD for a range of laminates

Open-Hole Tensile Results

- Average 1.02% decrease in strength with the DD-A laminate.
- However, for Hard1 E1 Quad the delamination due to blocked plies distributed the stress concentration leading to an artificially increased OHT strength.
- Taking the severe visual delamination point as failure of the Hard1 E1 Quad laminate, an average increase of 2.64% is seen for the DD-A laminates.

Laminate	Quad Layup	In-Plane (DD-A) Match
Soft	$[\pm 45/0/\pm 45/90/\pm 45]_s$	$[(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)]_{s2}/(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)]_T$
Quasi	$[0/45/90/-45]_s$	$[22.5/-67.5/67.5/-22.5]_4$
Hard1	$[45_2/0_4/-45_2/90_2]_s$	$[9/-61.5/61.5/-9]_5$
Hard2	$[45/0_2/-45/90_2/-45/0_2/45]_s$	

Open-Hole Tension

Open-hole tensile strength comparison Quad vs DD for a range of laminates

Open-Hole Compression Results

→ Average increase of 6.5% in open-hole compressive strength for the DD-A laminates

Open-hole compression strength comparison Quad vs DD for a range of laminates

Laminate	Quad Layup	In-Plane (DD-A) Match
Soft	$[\pm 45/0/\pm 45/90/\pm 45]_s$	$[(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)_{s2}/(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)]_T$
Quasi	$[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$	$[22.5/-67.5/67.5/-22.5]_4$
Hard1	$[45_2/0_4/-45_2/90_2]_s$	$[9/-61.5/61.5/-9]_5$
Hard2	$[45/0_2/-45/90_2/-45/0_2/45]_s$	

Open-Hole Compression

OHT DIC Results Example – Soft Laminates 325 MPa

Soft OHT Quad
 $[\pm 45/0/\pm 45/90/\pm 45_2]_s$

Soft OHT DD-A
 $[(31.5/-58.5/31.5/58.5)_{s2}/(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)]_T$

Axial Strain (ϵ_y)

Shear Strain (ϵ_{xy})

Calculation of average strain on a concentric circle (strain at distance from hole)

Conversion Framework Validation: Out-of-Plane

A framework has been established to convert any CFRP laminate to DD sub-laminate

Laminate	Quad Layup	Out-of-Plane (DD-D) Match
Soft	$[\pm 45/0/\pm 45/90/\pm 45]_s$	$[(27.5/-55.5/-27.5/55.5)_{s2}/(27.5/-55.5/-27.5/55.5)]_T$
Quasi	$[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$	$[9/-61/61/-9]_4$
Hard1	$[45_2/0_4/-45_2/90_2]_s$	$[9/-47/47/-9]_5$
Hard2	$[45/0_2/-45/90_2/-45/0_2/45]_s$	$[(7.5/-58/58/-7.5)_{s2}/(7.5/-58/58/-7.5)]_T$

Flexural modulus comparison Quad vs DD for a range of laminates

Flexural Strength Results

Flexural strength comparison Quad vs DD for a range of laminates

- Average 2.8% increase in strength using DD-D laminates.
- No clear trend to determine if Quad or DD laminates are superior in certain flexural scenarios.

Laminate	Quad Layup	Out-of-Plane (DD-D) Match
Soft	$[\pm 45/0/\pm 45/90/\pm 45_2]_s$	$[(27.5/-55.5/-27.5/55.5)_{s2}/(27.5/-55.5/-27.5/55.5)_1]_T$
Quasi	$[0/45/90/-45]_{2s}$	$[9/-61/61/-9]_4$
Hard1	$[45_2/0_4/-45_2/90_2]_s$	$[9/-47/47/-9]_5$
Hard2	$[45/0_2/-45/90_2/-45/0_2/45]_s$	$[(7.5/-58/58/-7.5)_{s2}/(7.5/-58/58/-7.5)_1]_T$

LVI and CAI Performance of DD Laminates

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LVI / CAI: Laminates

Thinner Laminates: 2.9mm using SEDD layout

Laminate	Quad Layout	In-Plane (SEDD-A) Match	Out-of-Plane (SEDD-D) Match
Thin-Soft	$[\pm 45/0/\pm 45/90/\pm 45]_s$	$[(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)_{s2}/(31.5/-58.5/-31.5/58.5)]_T$	$[(27.5/-55.5/-27.5/55.5)_{s2}/(27.5/-55.5/-27.5/55.5)]_T$
Thin-Hard1	$[45/0_2/-45/90_2/-45/0_2/45]_s$	$[(9/-61.5/61.5/-9)_{s2}/(9/-61.5/61.5/-9)]_T$	$[(7.5/-58/58/-7.5)_{s2}/(7.5/-58/58/-7.5)]_T$
		In-Plane (ExSEDD-A) Match	Out-of-Plane (ExSEDD-D) Match
Thin-Hard2	$[45/0_2/-45/0_2/45/0/-45/90]_s$	$[12/-57/0/57/-12]_{s2}$	$[9.5/-46.5/0/46.5/-9.5]_{s2}$

Thicker Laminates: 5.8 - 4.35 mm using conventional DD layout

Laminate	Quad Layout	In-Plane (DD-A) Match	Out-of-Plane (DD-D) Match
Thick-Quasi	$[0/45/90/-45]_{4s}$	$[22.5/-67.5/-22.5/67.5]_8$	$[17/-64.5/64.5/-17]_8$
Thin-Hard1	$[45/0_2/-45/90_2/-45/0_2/45]_{2s}$	$[9/-61.5/61.5/-9]_{10}$	
Thin-Hard2	$[0_2/45/-45/0_2/45/0_2/-45/90_2/45/0_2/-45]_s$	$[0/-53.5/53.5/0]_8$	$[0/-40/40/0]_8$
		In-Plane (ExDD-A) Match	Out-of-Plane (ExDD-D) Match
		$[12/-59/0/59/-12]_6$	$[7/-51.5/7/-7/51.5/-7]_5$

- 19 different laminates spanning a wide range of stiffness.
- In-plane and out-of-plane matched laminates compared.
- Both conventional DD and symmetry-enhanced (SEDD) laminates assessed.

In-plane LPP for all laminates

Out-of-plane LPP for all laminates

LVI Results

- LVI conducted in accordance with ASTM D7136.
- Post impact – NDT inspection – C-scan images.
- Delamination area computed used custom Python script.

Calibration applied and
area computed
1158.7 mm²

LVI Results

- LVI conducted in accordance with ASTM D7136.
- Post impact – NDT inspection – C-scan images.
- Delamination area computed used custom Python script.

Raw C-Scan

Area identified

Calibration applied and area computed
 → 1158.7 mm²

Thinner Laminates

Thicker Laminates

- Average 17.7% decrease in delamination area using DD-A laminates.
- Average 23.2% decrease in delamination area using DD-D laminates.

CAI Results

→ CAI testing in accordance with ASTM D7137.

→ 3D DIC carried out for thinner laminates.

CAI test with 3D DIC setup

Axial strain during CAI test

CAI Results

- CAI testing in accordance with ASTM D7137.
- 3D DIC carried out for thinner laminates.

CAI test with 3D DIC setup

Thinner Laminates

Thicker Laminates

- Similar CAI strength between Quad and DD-A laminates with average difference of 2.9%.
- Average 8.5% increase in CAI strength using DD-D laminates.
- Large variation in Hard thin CAI strength values due to buckling of the specimens – verified through DIC.

Summary

1. Proposed and validated robust homogenisation criteria & introduced Symmetry-Enhanced Double-Double (SEDD) Laminates

$$B^{Tr*} < 0.02$$

$$B^{Tr*} < 0.01$$

Summary

1. Proposed and validated robust homogenisation criteria & introduced Symmetry-Enhanced Double-Double (SEDD) Laminates.

2. Developed a framework to convert any laminate to DD laminate & assessed strength through various mechanical tests.

Summary

1. Proposed and validated robust homogenisation criteria & introduced Symmetry-Enhanced Double-Double (SEDD) Laminates.

2. Developed a framework to convert any laminate to DD laminate & assessed strength through various mechanical tests.

3. LVI and CAI testing assessing the performance of DD laminates and their comparison to Quad laminates.

Questions?

Homogenisation Paper

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Prof Stephen Tsai

